

**Curriculum and Assessment Review and
Music in Schools
Briefing and Analysis Paper**

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Introduction and context

The Curriculum and Assessment Review (CAR) *Building a world-class curriculum for all* was published on 5th November 2025, along with a response to its recommendations by the UK Government. It sets out ideas for developing a “world-leading curriculum” (p.23) and includes curriculum recommendations by subject. Music has been a subject which has suffered decline in GCSE and A-level entries. It has also seen problems with teacher supply over a number of years. These are both issues we have addressed in other briefing papers¹. Given these problems, the outcomes of the CAR are particularly acute for classroom music. This briefing paper considers the implications of the way CAR approaches music in schools and what this might mean for the future of the subject. It concentrates on four key areas, offering insight into the issues at stake, proposing possible solutions, and posing questions for further consideration.

¹ *Inter alia* Anderson, A. (2025) [Music Initial Teacher Training Bursary Briefing Paper](#) & Anderson, A. & Whittaker, A. (2025) [The State of Music Education in English Schools: A Landscape Briefing Paper](#).

1. Continued inequalities of music in schools

Understanding the issues

Music education is often characterised as a ‘postcode lottery’, with significant differences in the types, quantity, and availability of musical activities for young people across the country. At individual school level, the precise nature of musical activities is often determined in part by the skill set of the teacher, the characteristics of students a school serves, and the priority given to the subject by senior leadership teams. This means that there are substantial inequalities in the musical offer available to young people. The CAR presents data that bears this out. It states that the ‘Evidence of inequitable access to and success in Music is substantial’ (p. 97).

Table 19 of the Technical Annex, provides data on the proportion of state funded institutions with entries in Arts subjects at Key Stage 4, presented by disadvantage quintiles. The data for music is reproduced as Table 1.

Table 1 – Proportion of state-funded institutions with entries in Arts subjects at Key Stage 4 by disadvantage quintiles

Subject	Qualification type	Quintile 1 (least disadvantaged)	2	3	4	Quintile 5 (most disadvantaged)
Any Music	GCSE	90%	78%	63%	50%	39%
Any Music	Technical Award	10%	19%	27%	30%	34%
Any Music	GCSE or Technical Award	93%	89%	84%	76%	70%

Source: [Curriculum and Assessment Review: Analytical annex to the final report \(2025\)](#).

These data show that access to different kinds of music qualification at Key Stage 4 is stratified along disadvantaged lines. Overall, schools in the most disadvantaged areas are much less likely to have entries in music. Only 70% of institutions in the most disadvantaged quintiles entered a student for a music qualification. The schools in the least disadvantaged areas are much more likely to offer GCSE music than a Technical award. This raises questions about the equitable access to different kinds of qualifications for all young musicians. The proportions of GCSE entries decrease in the more disadvantaged quintiles, whereas the proportions of Technical

awards increase in the more disadvantaged quintiles. Such a layering of uptake along disadvantage lines across these awards is important to note, because it points to structural imbalances in what is being offered to children. A child cannot choose a qualification they are not offered. The importance of an 'offer', even if not taken up, is key.

The diversity of music qualifications available is often talked about as a strength of the sector – and aligns closely with the overall aims of the CAR to create appropriate assessment pathways for all young people – but there are systemic barriers to access here. Many schools only offer a single qualification and, as the data presented above shows, this often correlates with disadvantage. These more granular statistics reveal that unequal access to music qualifications is already clear at Key Stage 4, with significant implications for the opportunities of young people to continue their development at Key Stage 5.

Locally-based viewpoints are important in understanding this complex landscape. Music Hubs – the organisations tasked with coordinating and supporting musical activities – are often best-placed to know what qualifications are being offered in their locality and can help schools to consider their offer within the local landscape. This is important because the diversity of music qualifications, which range from courses focused on music production through to more traditional 'academic' music studies, could offer diverse progression pathways, but only where young people have a choice about the route they can take. The single offer available in a school may not be right for the individual in question.

Recommendations

- Support Hubs to have challenging conversations with schools around the appropriateness of qualification choice for their pupils
- Encourage coordination and collaboration between schools to ensure that a healthy diversity of qualifications are available locally.
- Incentivise schools to offer more than a single Music qualification offer at Key Stages 4 and 5. Small group sizes are often presented as a barrier to this, but a targeted incentive, especially in the most disadvantaged quintiles, could help unlock musical opportunity for young musicians.

Questions to ask

- How can data be shared in forms to enable local school leaders to make decisions on music qualification offers within the context of local conditions?
- Why are Technical awards offered in so few of the schools located in areas of least disadvantage?
- What incentives could help promote equality of access to music qualifications, so that all young people have a choice of offers locally?

2. Deprivation and music provision in schools

Understanding the issues

Access to music education in schools for young people continues to be problematic. There is an ongoing challenge in that music teacher supply is not as high as it needs to be to ensure there is a music teacher in every school. This can be seen from the music teacher vacancy rates from DfE figures (Table 2). This shows that in 2010-11 there were 16 vacant music teacher roles, whilst in 2025, there are 61. This is a vacancy rate of 0.2 in 2011 and 0.9 in 2025. During 2023-2024, the vacancy rate was even higher at 103 vacancies or a 1.5 vacancy rate. It is not possible to know whether the number of music teacher vacancies will increase or decrease for 2025-2026 as there have been between 44 and 103 vacancies between 2021 and 2025, showing wide variability. This is a significant difference from 2010-2017, where (with the exception of 2014-2015) the number of vacancies was never more than 29, which was a period of stability for music teacher recruitment.

Table 2 - Vacancy rate for secondary music teachers in England

Year	Number of vacancies	Vacancy rate
2010-2011	16	0.2
2011-2012	9	0.1
2012-2013	29	0.4
2013-2014	28	0.4
2014-2015	44	0.7
2015-2016	23	0.4
2016-2017	29	0.5
2017-2018	38	0.6
2018-2019	37	0.6
2019-2020	46	0.8
2020-2021	No data	No data
2021-2022	44	0.7
2022-2023	83	1.2
2023-2024	103	1.5
2024-2025	61	0.9

Source: DfE (28/5/25) vacancies secondary classroom teachers subject national 2010-2024. [School workforce data](#).

Retention rates for subjects are not publicly available, although in [response to a written question in February 2025](#), the DfE stated that:

- In the 2010/11 to 2014/15 academic years, 1,968 secondary school music teachers left the teaching profession.
- In the 2015/16 to 2019/20 academic years, 1,833 secondary school music teachers left the teaching profession
- In the 2020/21 to 2022/23 academic years, 1,068 secondary school music teachers left the profession.

To the best of our knowledge, the methodology DfE use to calculate these figures has not been detailed in public-facing documentation. However, Table 3 shows the comparison of these retention numbers to the total number of music teachers:

Table 3 - Comparison of total number of music teachers and music teacher retention 2010-2023

Years	Sum total of music teachers in these years	Numbers of music teachers who left the profession
2010-2015 ²	29,852	1,968
2015-2020	33,130	1,833
2020-2023	21,024	1,068
2010-2023	84,006	4,869

Source: DfE workforce_secondary_subjects_taught_2011_2024 School workforce data (June 2024 dataset)

It is worth noting that there is a proportional increase in 2020-2023 because this span represents 3 years only, but accounts for more than 50% of the previous figures.

In recent years, the number of unqualified teachers teaching music has increased from 250 teachers in 2010, to 363 in 2025 (Figure 2). Whilst the total number of teachers has increased from 6,290 in 2010 to 6,753 in 2025 (Figure 1), it is not clear whether this is to do with new DfE approaches to reporting on teacher numbers. Teachers are now listed as a “headcount”, and this may include school staff who teach music as a smaller proportion of their timetable, but for whom music is not their primary subject. This data is difficult to reconcile with the vacancy rate and due to what we assume may be new DfE counting methodologies³, it is difficult to ascertain the absolute number of subject specialist qualified music teachers in schools. We make this observation not to suggest that unqualified teachers may be providing

² As DfE figures run from 2011-2012, rather than 2010-11, it is likely the total number of teachers for the period 2010-2015 is higher than shown.

³ There has been a change in DfE teacher counting methodology in the (31/7/25) iteration of workforce data. In response to an enquiry about this, the DfE responded to us stating they had revised the “scaling methodology to more accurately account for non-teaching teachers, figures for earlier years...and...improved the scaling methodology in relation to the subject hours taught...[and] headcounts of subject teachers”. This means that in place of “teachers all years”, music teachers are now recorded under “headcount”. In addition, the highest subject qualification must now be chosen to isolate data sets. Selecting “any including none” and adding non-qualified and qualified staff together is the closest it is possible to come to understanding the number of music teachers. This figure is lower than the number of teachers the DfE previously used, and the DfE has also revised this historical data. Therefore, whilst figures can be compared within this data set (which are set out completely in Table 3), it is no longer possible to compare the number of teachers with those previously declared, including in answers to parliamentary questions and those we set out in: [Anderson, A & Whittaker, A. \(2025\) *The State of Music Education in English Schools: A Landscape Briefing Paper*](#)

lower quality education, but rather to represent changes in the nature of the music teaching workforce working in classrooms.

Figure 1 – Qualified secondary music teachers in England according to Key Stage

Source: DfE (28/5/25) workforce secondary specialist subjects taught 2010-2024 [School workforce data](#).

Figure 2 – Unqualified secondary music teachers in England according to Key Stage

Source: DfE (28/5/25) workforce secondary specialist subjects taught 2010-2024 [School workforce data](#).

There may still be tens of thousands of young people in schools who are unable to access music. The [CAR analytical annex](#) reports that 73% of young people were able to access music provision in some form. This means that of the 611,577 who were in Year 11 (15-16-year-olds) in 2023-2024, 165,126 of them may not have been able to access music. Schools with no arts offer at all at Key Stage 4 is stated to be 5% in the CAR, which means that 30,578 young people may **not** have been able to access any arts provision. Further levels of inequalities as reported in the CAR (see table 14 on p.20) are set out in Table 4. It should be noted that Table 4 does not give a complete picture, and if a young person has not accessed GCSE or a technical qualification, this does not mean that they have not been able to access other musical provision. Nevertheless, this table is useful for highlighting potential inequalities, because qualification data is one of the only ways that we can examine what is going on at school level from a national perspective.

Table 4 - Potential inequalities in music provision in schools as reported in the [Curriculum and Assessment Review Analytical Annex](#):

Total number of young people in Year 11 in 2023-2024	Category	Percentage	Raw numbers of young people accessing	Raw numbers of young people who may not be accessing
611,577	Schools with at least one entry in some form of music course	73%	446,451	165,126
611,577	Schools with at least one entry in GCSE music	57%	348,598	262,979
611,577	Schools with at least one entry in 'technical' music	19%	116,199	495,381
611,577	Schools without any entries in any arts subjects	5%	580,999	30,578

Source for percentages: [Curriculum and Assessment Review Analytical annex](#)

From the data presented in Tables 1–5, the precise situation in schools is not always clear. As such, there are some areas which require further investigation. The opportunities for young people to choose their arts pathway is determined by school approaches to timetables and these can vary widely. The retention rate for individual subjects (including music) cannot be found in publicly available datasets. There is currently no data that links areas of deprivation to music teacher staffing in schools. It is therefore difficult to know if young people are further deprived because of their school's curriculum offer. However, there are questions to ask about why the difference between least disadvantaged and most disadvantaged geographical areas in the CAR data results in GCSE music entries differing by 51% and why technical awards differ by 24%⁴.

Recommendations

- Require schools to record their rationales for arts provision, and to include this in Ofsted reporting.
- Make data into areas of deprivation and music teacher supply public, so that Hubs and schools can understand any decisions they may make within their context
- Target music teacher training with an additional one-off bursary incentive for training music teachers to work in deprived areas for 5 years. We calculate that this additional one-off bursary of £2,000 in these areas could be provided for a total payment of £300,000.
- Support music development in deprived areas with a music premium for secondary schools. For the 149 schools in the most deprived local authority districts in England outside London, we suggest that schools could receive £1,000 per music teacher for an investment of £149,000.

⁴ See table 19 of the [Curriculum and Assessment Review Analytical annex](#), which reports that 90% of the least disadvantaged areas have entries in GCSE music, while 39% have GCSE music entries in the least disadvantaged areas. For Music technicals, 10% have entries in the least disadvantaged areas, while 36% have entries in the most disadvantaged areas.

Questions to ask

- When will data on music teacher supply compared to levels of deprivation begin to be gathered by the DfE?
- Why is school-level data on classroom music teacher retention considered unimportant?
- Why has the DfE counting methodology for the number of secondary music teachers changed?
- What role do Ofsted play in evaluating schools' offers in arts and music provision?

3. The status of composing in schools

Understanding the issues

The status of composing is unclear in the CAR. Whilst 'music' is mentioned 86 times, and music 'performing' or 'performance' is included four times, 'composition' receives only one mention, and the act of 'composing' is not referenced. Composing has been given less status and ascribed value, but we know that the opportunity for children to compose (including in areas of deprivation) makes a significant difference to their musical and creative educational experience. Our project report for [Listen Imagine Compose Primary](#) addresses this area. This project worked with 8 primary schools in Birmingham and Bristol over two years with 9 professional composers working with 16 classes of Year 4 and Year 5 children. Our findings included noting that composing increases children's confidence and pride in sharing their ideas, increased their capacity for collaborative working, and developed their identities (p.15-16). We recommended that composing be given a higher profile within the curriculum (p.30).

Ofsted also note the importance of composing in schools, and so its absence in the CAR is surprising. In their 2023 report [Striking the Right Note](#), Ofsted state:

A high quality music curriculum is likely to...include opportunities for pupils to develop and practise the components of composition that are set out in the

school's curriculum [and] includes tasks...that are appropriate for pupils to be able to realise their expressive intentions. (p. 26)

Composing breaks down stereotypes and social boundaries, enables diverse musicality and develops young people's ability to respond and express themselves in music.

Recommendations

- Ensure composing is retained in the new generation of Key Stage 4 specifications, with an equal weighting to performing assessment.
- Require Music Hubs to develop a costed composing strategy and provide provision and support in composing as well as performing. If music hubs allocated 10% of their budgets to composing, this would result in a national investment of £790,000, equivalent to just £0.10 per child.
- Establish a composing access fund from a strategic board of commercial partners to enable equitable and accessible composing of all genres at the school point of access. An investment of £74,500 focused on the five most deprived areas of England outside London would enable composing development projects to a value of £500 per secondary school, which could be transformative, for just the cost of £0.46 per child.

Questions to ask

- What is being done to develop the next generation of composing talent in our schools?
- What undertaking can be given about the importance of composing in schools?
- What proportion of the £79 million of hub funding is spent on composing?

4. The removal of the EBacc and music in schools

Understanding the issues

One of the major discussion points for music in response to the CAR was the retirement of the EBacc. The EBacc (a school performance measure made up of particular subject groups, which excluded the Arts) has long been seen as a contributing factor to the decline of arts education within mainstream schools. There are many in the sector who, rightly, see the change from the EBacc as a really positive moment for music and creative education in schools. Whilst the headline is that the EBacc has been discontinued, Progress 8 – which was its underpinning – remains and this is important. It remains unclear whether this broader framework of the EBacc will be discontinued in full in practice, but it is clear that its title is to be replaced with ‘academic breadth’. The Curriculum and Assessment Review states:

...we recommend the removal of the EBacc measure but the retention of the EBacc ‘bucket’ in Progress 8 under the new title of ‘Academic Breadth’. (p.10)

In the Government response, the proposals for the reform of Progress 8 are based on two ‘breadth’ slots which must include representation from two of these three categories (UK Government Response, pp. 45–46):

- Humanities
- Creative subjects
- Languages

This is a major change because creative subjects are now likely to be considered within the remit of this performance measure. This is positive news for music education, placing creative subjects on an equal footing in a way not possible for the last decade or so. These subjects are to be constituted as giving academic breadth to the rounded education a young person is entitled to receive. It is, however, important to note that none of the current documentation specifies what constitutes a

'Creative subject'.⁵ This is significant because the broad categorisation opens up opportunities for young people to pursue creative subjects where they might have otherwise been structurally prevented from doing so. As such, this presents a valuable opportunity for music provision to be expanded within schools and, consequently, continuation of music through to Key Stage 4 to be more easily justified.

It will be important to monitor the impact of these changes closely over the coming years. The structure as proposed in the [Government response \(p. 46\)](#) (presented as the bottom image of Figure 3) would enable a school to make changes to incorporate creative subjects into their Key Stage 4 performance measurements. However, the structure also leaves space for a school to continue to operate in exactly the same way as they have done under the EBacc, leaving out the 'Creative' subject block altogether. A comparison of the old and new structures, as shown in Figure 3 demonstrates the similarities in broad structure between the existing and newly proposed Progress 8 measures.

⁵ The working assumption is that these are subjects that would be represented in the disciplines of the National Centre for the Arts and Music Education, due to launch in September 2026. See DfE, ['Young people to benefit from creative education boost'](#) (18 March 2025).

Figure 3 - Existing Progress 8 structure (top) (Ofsted, 2018) and newly proposed Progress 8 configuration (bottom) (CAR Government Response, 2025, p. 46).

The ways that these changes will be enacted is something that all those involved in music education will need to be attentive to if the removal of the EBacc is to be capitalised on for creative education. The current proposals represent an opportunity for change but also leave space to maintain the status quo. What will matter in the long run is not exactly what is in these proposals but how these are enacted in all schools. The practical outworkings within individual schools will be the determining factor as to whether these changes help to alleviate current inequalities or sustain similar trends.

Owing to many years of the EBacc determining subject options for many young people at Key Stage 4, there may not be adequate capacity within all schools to

immediately restore arts provision, particularly where it has been cut already. The data presented in Table 1 demonstrates that there are shortcomings in offer in some of the most disadvantaged schools, and so careful attention may need to be given to support the restarting of creative subjects at Key Stage 4.

Recommendations

- Commission a targeted review of national curriculum provision within one year of the removal of the EBacc to understand if curriculum provision in schools has changed
- Immediately restore PGCE bursaries to creative subjects, to help incentivise new teachers into the profession
- Provide opportunities for schools to pool expertise and resources, unlocking diverse expertise and supporting teachers working alone to expand their practice.
- Establish an arts start-up premium, to help pump prime creative education in areas of particular need. Targeted provision could involve the off-setting of exam entry fees, grants towards bringing in specialist expertise, or contributions towards the cost of repairing or purchasing equipment.

Questions to ask

- What are the expectations for schools with the new notion of ‘academic breadth’?
- How will ‘academic breadth’ be monitored and reviewed at local, regional, and national levels?
- What are the incentives for schools to make changes to their current established practice? How will a renewed sense of academic breadth be promoted?

Summary

In this briefing paper, we have set out to dig a little deeper into some of the details of the Curriculum and Assessment Review and consider its implications for music education. The four key areas of interest are all elements that will need careful monitoring over the coming years. There are inequalities of music access already

baked into the system as it currently stands, and it will be important to ensure that such barriers can be dismantled as the recommendations of the Curriculum and Assessment Review are put into place. Of particular concern across all the points in this paper is the clear and sustained connection between levels of deprivation and reduced opportunity to access music education. If the aims of a world-leading education system are to be achieved, all pupils must be able to access a sustained and high-quality music education. It is therefore vitally important that music and the creative arts are approached respectfully and meaningfully by those responsible for the implementation of this new review. A decade of systemic decline and challenge has left the sector with much reduced capacity to respond positively to such a moment of change. Therefore, our recommendations are presented in the spirit of ongoing development, grounded in the view that music teachers are best-placed to respond to the needs of their learners, but that they need targeted professional development in order to be able to achieve this and advocate for the place of creativity in a future-ready curriculum.

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